

Acute neurophysiological effects of neuromuscular manual therapy in intensive care unit

Rosa Grazia Bellomo^{2 A-F}, Giovanni Barassi^{4 A-F}, Tullio Spina^{5 A-F}, Matilde Del Duca^{1 A-F},
Piera Attilia Di Felice^{1 A-F}, Raoul Saggini^{3 A-F}

¹ Faculty of Physiotherapy "G.d'Annunzio" University-Chieti

² Associated Professor of School of Specialties in PRM, Department of Medicine and Science of Aging, "G.d'Annunzio" University, Chieti, Italy

³ Full Professor of School of Specialties in PRM, "G. d'Annunzio" University, Chieti, Italy Department of Medical Sciences, Oral and Biotechnology, "G.d'Annunzio" University, Chieti, Italy

⁴ Coordinator of Faculty of Physiotherapy "G.d'Annunzio" University-Chieti

⁵ Department of Emergency Urgency Medicine "Santo Spirito" Hospital of Pescara

Received: December 06, 2017 Accepted: December 18, 2017

Abstract

With the term "severe acquired brain injury" (ABI) we mean a damage, of traumatic or other nature (hypoxic, infective, vascular) origin, capable of inducing a coma state (Glasgow Coma Scale GCS=<8), or moto-sensory impairment, and/or cognitive-comportamental impairment, which involve serious disability [2]. The overall recovery after a TBI is a direct consequence of physical, cognitive and behavioral residual abilities. The aim of our study is to collect clinical and rehabilitative datas, through the application of a neuromuscular manual therapy protocol on a selected sample of patients recovered in intensive care Unit. Patients included in the blind randomized trial were recruited following specific inclusion and exclusion criteria and then they underwent a therapeutical protocol of neuromuscular manual therapy (NMT). Vital parameters considered (HR, BR, O2S and BP) were monitored using advanced digital systems deriving from the usage of specific invasive and no-invasive medical aids present in the Intensive Care department. Patients underwent neuromuscular manual therapy sessions executed one a day for 7 to 10 sessions per patient, vital parameters of patients were collected The results of this study demonstrated a mean reduction in heart rate, a reduction in systolic blood pressure, a reduction in diastolic blood pressure, a reduction in mean arterial pressure, an average decrease in respiratory rate and finally a slight increase in the oxygen's saturation

Keywords: Rehabilitation, Brain injury, Manual Therapy

Introduction

The term "severe acquired brain injury" (ABI) mean a damage, of traumatic or other nature (hypoxic, infective, vascular) origin, capable of inducing a coma state (Glasgow Coma Scale GCS=<8), or moto-sensory impairment, and/or cognitive-comportamental impairment, which involve serious disability [2]. From this definition are excluded chronic-degenerative pathologies and outcomes of various cerebral damages with different kind of etiology without the induction of a coma state. According to epidemiological datas [1], cranial traumas in rehabilitation departments for ABI actually represent almost 1/3 of the whole casuistry (in the past were about the 50%), while others 2/3 are represented by patients with cerebrovascular lesions and post-anoxic encephalopathies with a less favorable or an unfavorable outcome. Furthermore the mean age has progressively increased from 1990 to today (from 25 years old in 1990, to 35 years old in 2000, to 50 years old in 2010) and also comorbidities increased at the same time.[1]

The rehabilitation of people with Severe Acquired Brain Injury (ABI) is an important concern to be approached with a comprehensive program aimed to improve the recovery of patients. The efficacy of an early and intensive rehabilitation program has been shown in large number of studies. [2-4]

ABI can result from both traumatic or non-traumatic events.

Traumatic brain injuries (TBI) are the leading cause of death.[5,6] The incidence of TBI ranges between 91 to 546 every 100000 inhabitants per year.[7,8]

Such variability is probably due to different inclusion criteria adopted. A recent review estimated the incidence of TBI to 243 cases every 100000 inhabitants per year.[9]

Few studies focused on the prevalence of TBI and the data are often extrapolated in indirect ways. A Danish study reported in 317 over 100000 the number of subjects unable to return to work after the TBI.[9] A recent analysis according to the projections of the Center of Disease Control reported a prevalence of

TBI in 1893 out of 100000 inhabitants per year. [8,10]

Also the severity of the trauma was considered according to different criteria and scales. Excluding studies with a major selection bias the following proportion in TBI severity was considered: 9 minor: 220; moderate: 14; severe: 9.

The evaluation of the outcome measures in TBI patients is influenced, as in the epidemiological studies, by both selection bias and diagnostic criteria adopted [11-13].

Moreover the small amount of the populations studied greatly reduces the validity of the available results.

The European Brain Injury Consortium (EBIC) study [11] included 796 subjects with severe TBI with a GCS ranging between 3 and 8 at admission. Also in severe cases the 6-month outcome clearly demonstrated an improvement in disability scores.

The overall recovery after a TBI is a direct consequence of physical, cognitive and behavioral residual abilities. Sometimes even if an excellent physical performance can be demonstrated, the presence of a residual relevant cognitive or behavior impairment may seriously compromise the prognosis of TBI victims. [14]

The National Center for Injury Prevention and Control is part of the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) in the USA. In 1995 the Center produced guidelines for the surveillance of central nervous system injury, to facilitate the collection of comparable epidemiological data across the USA and thus further prevention and control efforts. [31]

The guidelines provide definitions, data items, and methods for designing and implementing surveillance plans and analysis of data.

Both a 'clinical case definition' (for uncoded data) and a 'uniform data systems case definition' (a list of ICD-9 codes—see Table 2.4) are given. Under the clinical case definition TBI is defined either

- as an occurrence of injury to the head that is documented in a medical record, with one or more of the following conditions attributed to head injury: observed or self reported decreased level of consciousness; amnesia; skull fracture; objective neurological or neuropsychological abnormality; diagnosed intracranial lesion, or
- as an occurrence of death resulting from trauma, with head injury listed on the death certificate, autopsy report, or medical examiner's report in the sequence of conditions that resulted in death. [31]

The CDC definitions are used in a number of state-based traumatic brain injury and spinal cord injury surveillance programs throughout the USA. [31]

The CDC uniform data systems case definition has recently been adopted by the Research Center for Injury Studies in Australia in its work on traumatic brain injury. [32]

AIM

The rehabilitation of people with Severe Acquired Brain Injury (ABI) is an important concern to be approached with a comprehensive program aimed to improve the recovery of patients. The efficacy of an early and intensive rehabilitation program has been shown in large number of studies. While, few studies focused on the prevalence of TBI and the data are often extrapolated in indirect ways. [14]

According to what the literature established and being known that the profound manual pressures, performed in a statistical manner or with slow movements, besides encourage the transformation "gel to sol" of the fundamental substance of the connective fascia (thanks to its thixotropic properties), stimulates Ruffini's mecanoceptors (especially for tangential forces) and a part of interstitial inducing an increase of the vagal activity with the relative effect on autonomic activities including a global relaxation of all muscles and also of the mind. An opposed result is obtained using fast and strong manual approaches (manipulations, vibrations, beatings, etc.) which stimulate Pacini's receptors. [15,16]

It has been decided to use a rehabilitative protocol, based on neuromuscular manual therapy, within the Chair of Physical and Rehabilitative Medicine of the "G. d'Annunzio" University of Chieti-Pescara, on a selected sample of patients hospitalized in the intensive care unit of "S. S. Spirito" Hospital of Pescara. An increasing literature demonstrates that patients surviving to a severe critical disease usually report significant and prolonged neuromuscular complications which damage their physical function and the quality of life after the discharge from the hospital.

Constriction in bed, infusional medical therapies and their associated mechanisms, can play an important role in the pathogenesis of the neuromuscular damage in critical patients.

A new approach for the management of patients subjected to a mechanical ventilation includes the reduction of profound sedation and the increase of rehabilitative therapies and early mobilizations after the recovery in the intensive care department. Due to the role that the Neuromuscular Manual Therapy plays within a global and advanced rehabilitative process and on the base of neurophysiological principles at its base it seemed clear including this science inside the rehabilitative process prescribed to the patients during intensive care.

The aim of our study is to collect clinical and rehabilitative data, through the application of a neuromuscular manual therapy protocol on a selected sample of patients recovered in intensive care.

Concretely we proceeded by detecting the following vital parameters: heart rate (HR), breath rate (BR), oxygen saturation (O2S) and blood pressure (BP),

before the neuromuscular manual therapy treatment and after it.

Materials and methods

In the “S. Spirito” Hospital of Pescara 10 patients were recruited in the intensive care unit. Patients included in the blind randomized trial were recruited following specific inclusion and exclusion criteria (showed in the table 1) and then underwent a therapeutical protocol of neuromuscular manual therapy (NMT). Vital parameters considered (HR, BR, O2S and BP) were monitored using advanced digital systems deriving from the usage of specific invasive and no-invasive medical aids present in the Intensive Care Unit. The protocol, besides the inclusion criteria of the sample studied, gave us also an anamnestic

prospect of the examined patient (see table 2): the list of the six distinct anatomical districts treated with the neuromuscular manual therapy and specifications on the applied techniques. In the end datas have been included in a specific informatic grid in order to be analyzed by a calculator software to carry out a statistical analysis of the results obtained.

The randomized trial was approved by the local ethics committee in accordance with the Helsinki Declaration and all subjects involved in the study have been informed about the procedure and the aim of the research and signed the informed consent.

According to the complexity of patients selected following inclusion and exclusion criteria, at the general

Table n.1: NCLUSION AND EXCLUSION CRITERIAS	
<p>INCLUSION CRITERIA</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SEVERE ACQUIRED BRAIN INJURY (ABI) • INTRACEREBRAL HEMORRAGE • ISCHEMIC AND HEMORRAGIC STROKE • VENOUS THROMBOSIS • COMA GCS = < 8 • SENSORY-MOTOR AND COGNITIVE-COMPORTAMENTAL ALTERATION (WITH DISABILITIES) • AGE BETWEEN 18 AND 75 YEARS OLD • TREATMENT LASTING BETWEEN 7 AND 10 SESSIONS 	<p>EXCLUSION CRITERIA</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AGE UNDER 18 AND OVER 75 YEARS OLD • ACTIVE INFECTION • BODY TEMPERATURE OVER 37°C • CANCER • TRAUMATIC TORACI-ABDOMINAL DAMAGE • ICP (INTRACRANIC PRESSURE PRESENCE) • DYNAMIC CEREBRAL INSTABILITY NOT FARMACOLOGICALLY CONTROLLED • HEMODYNAMIC INSTABILITY NOT FARMACOLOGICALLY CONTROLLED

Table n.2: CLINIC-ANAMNESTIC PROSPECT			
Surname	Name	Age	Diagnosis
DATE OF THE EVENT	DATE OF INTENSIVE CARE UNIT RECOVERY		
<p>ETIOLOGY Etiology (multiple answers allowed) -Traumatic -Anoxic -Hemorrhagic -Ischemic -Infective -Neoplastic -Other</p> <p>PRIMARY DAMAGE EVALUATION Location of the damage -diffusion -focus -Emisphere Dx Sx Bilateral -Posterior cranial fossa -Encefalic trunk</p> <p>ASSOCIATED TRAUMATIC DAMAGES -Limb bones -Spine bones -Spinal cord -Toracic-Abdomen -Facial -PNS -Senory organs -Other (specify)</p> <p>PREVIOUS COMORBIDITY (multiple answers allowed) -Cardiovascular -Respiratory -Endocrine/metabolic -Neoplastic -Psichiatric -Infective Neurologic - Other (specify)</p> <p>SEVERITY OF COMA AT THE BEGINNING - GLASGOW COMA SCALE total score (choose the worst score of the first 24 hours after the rianimator maneuvers)</p> <p>MONITORATION OF BASAL VITAL FUNCTIONS -ICP MONITOR si no</p> <p>DYNAMIC CEREBRAL INSTABILITY (necessity of intracranial pressure therapies or amines to keep the perfusion) yes no</p> <p>DYNAMIC VASCULAR INSTABILITY (necessity of vasopressor drugs, antihypertensive drugs, amines) yes no</p> <p>HYDROCEFALUS No DVE DVP (deliquoration or ventricular dilatations)</p> <p>BREATHING AUTONOMY -SB (spontaneous breathing) -CV (controlled ventilation) -AV (assisted ventilation) -NIV (non invasive ventilation)</p>			

overview supplied at the clinical prospective, at their placement in the bed, at the pharmacological therapy in progress and at the necessity of the whole multidisciplinary equipe, have been identified 6 muscular districts on which it was possible to base the therapeutic protocol:

- Peroneous Brevis, Peroneous Third and Peroneous Longus
- Ileo-Psoas
- Diaphragm
- Levator Scapula
- Pectoralis Minor
- Quadratus Plantae

The neuromuscular manual therapy sessions has been executed one a day for 7 to 10 sessions per patient, vital parameters of patients are collected thanks to their continuous monitoring, invasive and non invasive, before and after the neuromuscular manual therapy.

After the individuation of the muscular district to treat it was possible to define the neuromuscular manual therapy protocol.

The first step forecast the collection of vital parameters and the signaling of the usage of eventual analgesedative drugs to report in the overlying table.

2° STEP: NEUROMUSCULAR TREATMENT OF THE QUADRATUS PLANTAE (INCLUDING METATARSALS AREAS AND FINGER FLEXORS)

The patients lied in supine position. The preparation of the soft tissues of the examined areas is made applying a circular manipulation with fingers using the technique of efflurage. Then will be made a specific circular friction increasingly deeper on the muscular bellies, metatarsal areas and the insertion points using inches.(Figure I-II). Finally we proceed with the usage of knuckles on the plantar aponeurosis moving in a distal-proximal direction, concluding on the whole heel with a transversal friction and direct pressure using the inch or knuckles (Figure III- IV).

3°STEP: TREATMENT OF THE PERONEOUS MUSCLES (LATERAL AREA)

The patient lies on the bed in supine position while the physiotherapist is on the side. It is applied a

bellies, on stiff bands insertional points of the Peroneous Brevis, Peroneous Third and Peroneous Longus using inches.(Figure V)

4°STEP: TREATMENT OF THE ILEO-PSOAS

The patient lies in supine position while the physiotherapist is on the side of the bed. With the fingertip we can localize the psoas laterally to the abdomen at the navel level, then with a deep pression we can moove with a 45° angle compared to the vertical line to termine the movement with the technique of the transversal longitudinal friction reaching the groin area. (Figure VI).

It is necessary to be gentle because of the health state of the intensive care patient and because of the connection between these muscles and the abdominal organs.

5°STEP: TREATMENT OF THE DIAPHRAGM

The patient lies in supine position while the physiotherapist is on the side of the bed. Use inches with the efflurage technique on the two emidiaphragms to prepare the tissues to treat following mediolateral way, from the xiphoid area to the ipocondrial areas (Figure VIII-IX).

6°STEP: TREATMENT OF THE PECTORALIS MINOR

The patient lies in supine position with the arm on the side of the body while the physiotherapist is on the head of the bed. Using the finger tip press deep through the Pectoralis Major to perfectly isolate myotendineous junction of the Pectoralis Minor, placed about 5 cm under the coracoid process. The technique is applied by transversal longitudinal friction on the muscle belly ending with circular movements (Figure X).

7°STEP: TRETAMENT OF THE LEVATOR SCAPULA

The patient lies in supine position while the physiotherapist is on the side or the head of the bed. stretching techniques and transversal friction on the cervical lordosis passage area right under the insertion of C4 were used (Figure XI-XII).

1° STEP: COLLECTION OF VITAL PARAMETERS (Before treatment)			
Data trattamento		Before treatment	After treatment
Saturation (O2S)		97	
Heart rate (HR)		100	
Breath rate (BR)		25	
Radial and femural blood pressure (BP)		165/75	
MAP* Mean arterial preessure		105	
AlalgoSedation Prescribed drugs			

*MAP=((2(Dp) + Sp)/3) Dp= diastolic pressure Sp= sistolic pressure)

transversal longitudinal pressure friction on muscle

Figure 1. Circular Friction

Figure 2. Circular Friction

Figure 3. Plantar fasciae Treatment

Figure 4. Treat of calcaneal area

Figure 5. Longitudinal and transversal friction on muscle bellies

Figure 6. Ileo-psoas: manual treatment

Figure 7. Longitudinal and transversal friction on ileo-psoas

Figure 10. Pectoralis minor: manual treatment

Figure 8. Effleurage on diaphragm

Figure 11. Levator Scapula: Stretching technique

Figure 9. Digitopressure on diaphragm

Figure 12. Levator Scapula: manual treatment

Date of treatment		Before treatment	After treatment
Saturation (O2S)		97	98
Heart Rate (HR)		100	95
Breath Rate (BR)		25	23
Radial and femoral blood pressure (BP)		165/75	160/68
MAP* Mean Arterial Pressure		105	98.6666
AnalgoSedation Prescribed drugs			

The compressive duration of the treatment for each side of the body is about 25/30 minutes. When terminated, vital parameters will be reported in the specific grid.

N°10										
29/10/2015	100	100	66	64	23	21	135/75	128/64	95	85.33
Sedation NO										

4.2 GRAPHS AND DATAS

The graphs report the mean values at time T0 and T1 of every single vital parameter investigated on the whole sample in.

Figure A) HEART RATE (HR)

Heart Rate: the mean of the values collected at time T0 and T1 are respectively **81,23077** and **77.76923**; we can highlight a decrease of this parameter of **3.461539**. This difference seems to be significant and not determined by the case as showed by the results of the two statistical tests (T-test e Wilcoxon test), infact making those test the percentage of probability allowing to exclude the null hypothesis was less then 0,05.

Prob Level= 0.00000 T-Statistic= 7.4709

Standard Deviation: T0=16.51833 T1=16.16146

Figure B) BREATH RATE (BR)

Breath Rate: the mean of the values collected at time T0 and T1 are respectively **821,80769** and **20,41026** ; we can highlight a decrease of this parameter of **1,397436**. This difference seems to be significant and not determined by the case as showed by the results of the two statistical tests (T-test e Wilcoxon test), infact making those test the percentage of probability allowing to exclude the null hypothesis was less then 0,05.

Prob Level= 0,000007 T-Statistic= 4,9397

Standard Deviation: T0= 5,603936 T1= 4,420836

Figure C) MAXIMAL ARTERIAL BLOOD PRESSURE (BP MAX)

Maximal Arterial Blood Pressure: the mean of the values collected at time T0 and T1 are respectively **126,0128** and **121,9615** ; we can highlight a decrease of this parameter of **4,051282**. This difference seems to be significant and not determined by the case as showed by the results of the two statistical tests (T-test e Wilcoxon test), infact making those test the percentage of probability allowing to exclude the null hypothesis was less then 0,05.

Prob Level= 0,00006 T-Statistic= 4,2546

Standard Deviation: T0=16,36396 T1=16,48017

Figure D) MINIMAL ARTERIAL BLOOD PRESSURE (BP MIN)

Minimal Arterial Blood Pressure: the mean of the values collected at time T0 and T1 are respectively **71,21795** and **68,32051** ; we can highlight a decrease of this parameter of **4,0663**. This difference seems to be significant and not determined by the case as showed by the results of the two statistical tests (T-test e Wilcoxon test), infact making those test the percentage of probability allowing to exclude the null hypothesis was less then 0,05.

Prob Level= 0.00000 T-Statistic= 6,2931

Standard Deviation: T0=8,784058 T1=8,254859

Figure E) MEAN ARTERIAL BLOOD PRESSURE (BP)

Mean Arterial Blood Pressure: the mean of the values collected at time T0 and T1 are respectively **90,02295** and **86,41718** ; we can highlight a decrease of this parameter of **3,605769**. This difference seems to be significant and not determined by the case as showed by the results of the two statistical tests (T-test e Wilcoxon test), infact making those test the percentage of probability allowing to exclude the null hypothesis was less then 0,05.

Prob Level= 0.00000 T-Statistic= 8,9503

Standard Deviation: T0=8,713993 T1=8,072546

Figure F) SATURATION (O2S)

Saturation: the mean of the values collected at time T0 and T1 are respectively **98,41026** and **99,01282** ; we can highlight an increase of this parameter of **0,625641**. This difference seems to be significant and not determined by the case as showed by the results of the two statistical tests (T-test e Wilcoxon test), infact making those test the percentage of probability allowing to exclude the null hypothesis was less then 0,05.

Prob Level= 0.00000

T-Statistic= 5,2646

Standard Deviation: T0=1,2937 T1=1,012822

Figure G) MEAN VALUES T0 IN VS MEAN VALUES T1 OUT (FIRST VS LAST DAY OF TREATMENT)

Minimal Arterial Blood Pressure: this is the only vital parameter that the statistical analysis on the long period highlighted with significant values. It reports the mean values collected at time T0 (first day of treatment) and T1

(last day of treatment) which are respectively of **70,33334** and **63,5**; we can highlight a decrease of the parameter, in the long period of about **6,833333**. This difference seems to be significant and not determined by the case as showed by the results of the two statistical tests (T-test e Wilcoxon test), in fact making those test the percentage of probability allowing to exclude the null hypothesis was less than 0,05.

Prob Level= 0,04017 T-Statistic= 2,7530

Standard Deviation: T0=5,501515 T1=2,588436

Results

The results of this study showed a mean reduction in heart rate equal to 3.461539 beats per minute, a reduction in systolic blood pressure of 4.051282 mmHg, a decrease reduction in diastolic blood pressure 4.0663 mmHg, a reduction in mean arterial pressure of 3.605769 mm Hg. It could be suggested that manual therapy is able to allow the rebalancing of coordinated work between the gaming system nervous sympathetic and parasympathetic, in fact it is mediated by activation dermal and subdermal pressure of receptors innervated by the fibers afferent vagal as affirmed by Campo etc. [17-20]

Besides the interstitial mechanoreceptors activation affects the autonomic nervous system causing it to vary the local pressure of arterioles and capillaries present in the connective tissue, thus affecting the plasma pass from the vessels to the extracellular matrix thus varying the local viscosity. Furthermore, the manual stimulation, through deep pressure and slow movements, of the interstitial receptors, as well as that of Ruffini receptors, is able to increase the vagal tone (parasympathetic nervous system) generating global organic changes which have a profound and beneficial relaxation.[21-24]

These receptors, everywhere in the body (including meninges and visceral ligaments and maximum concentration in the periosteum), represent the family of nerve receptors. The sensory fibers of muscular innervation derive only about 25% from well-known Golgi receptors, Ruffini, Pacini and Paciniform (fiber type I and II), while all the rest originates from "interstitial receptors" (fiber type III and IV). About 90% of the interstitial receptors are demyelinated (type IV), while the remaining possess a thin myelin sheath (type III). For slower action than the receptors I and II, in the past were considered mostly nociceptors, thermo and chemoreceptors (sensitive to vibrations with frequencies below 100 Hz). In fact, many of them are multimodal and in the majority mechanoreceptors (sensitive to touch, pressure and traction) divided into two sub-groups, of approximately equal numbers, according to their activation threshold pressure stimuli: Low-threshold pressure (LTP) and high-threshold pressure (HTP). There are interstitial receptors to slow or quick adaptation. The activation, in certain disease states of interstitial receptors is sensitive to painful stimuli or mechanical (mostly

HTP) can generate pain syndromes in the absence of the classic nerve irritation (eg. Radicular compressions). This sensory network, in addition to having an afferent function for detecting the positioning and movement of the body segments, influence, by means of intimate connections, the autonomic nervous system about functions such as the regulation of blood pressure, heart rate and breathing, tuning to very precisely to the needs local tissue [28]. The interstitial mechanoreceptors activation affects the autonomic nervous system causing it to vary the local pressure of arterioles and capillaries present in the connective tissue, thus affecting the plasma pass from the vessels to the extracellular matrix thus varying the local viscosity [30]. Furthermore, the manual stimulation, through deep pressure and slow movements, of the interstitial receptors, as well as that of Ruffini receptors, is able to increase the tone vagal (parasympathetic nervous system) generating global organic changes which have a profound and beneficial relaxation. [20-24,29]

It has been showed also a mean reduction of the breathing frequency of 1,397436 breaths per minute and, in the end, an increase in the oxygen saturation of 0,6025641 Spo2 has been underlined at T1. Even more it is noticed a reduction in the circulating level of substance P, considered cause of pain [25], and an increase in the pain stimulatory threshold, reducing so the alarm reaction [26-27].

Moreover, one single session of fascial massage demonstrated a reduction of the activity of the sympathetic nervous system and a major activation of the parasympathetic nervous system with a reduction of symptoms like anxiety, depression, pain and an improvement of mood.[27]

Even more, M. Diego and T. Field have conducted deep researches demonstrating that the massage with a moderate pressure could modulate the passage from the sympathetic to the parasympathetic activity while with a gentle pressure it was noted a little sympathetic response or at least no response at all. In their study on the effects of vibratory stimulations, light variations and moderate pressure massage, the decrease of the heart rate, the anxiety and stress was noted in all the three methods,, but the major results were obtained using the manual treatment. [33]

These differences seem to be significant and not determined by the case as showed by the results of the two statistical tests (T-test e Wilcoxon test), in fact the percentage of probability allowing to exclude the null hypothesis was less than 0,05. In the end it was considered, for each single parameter, the effect of the treatment in the long period, and so considering the values at time T0 (first day of treatment) and time T1 (last day of treatment). From this analysis it appeared to be significant only the reduction of the mean arterial diastolic pressure, with a decrease of 6,833333 mmHg.

CONCLUSIONS

The treatment protocol of neuromuscular therapy within the Chair of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation at the University of Chieti, directed by prof. Raoul Saggini at the intensive care unit of "S. Spirito" of Pescara, has reflected the theoretical principles that similar studies previously conducted have wanted to highlight.

The results of this study demonstrated a mean reduction in heart rate, a reduction in systolic blood pressure, a reduction in diastolic blood pressure, a reduction in mean arterial pressure, an average decrease in respiratory rate and finally a slight increase in the oxygen's saturation.

Ultimately, were considered, for each parameter, the effects of the treatments in the long period, considering the values at T0 the first day of neuromuscular therapy and the value at time T1 the last treatment day. This analysis was significant only for the mean of diastolic blood pressure. Our experience has allowed us to understand the importance of neuromuscular therapy as part of critically ill patients, and the same patients have allowed us to understand what are the limits of applicability of such neuromuscular manual therapy. That are separate limits precisely the complexity of the welfare state undergone by the critically ill patient, the physiological conditions due to drug interaction with various organ systems, the possible dependence ventilation, as well as from the many problems that the underlying disease entails.

We can say that the intensive care unit thanks to advanced electronic systems for the detection of vital signs, gave us the opportunity to have a parametric feedback that clearly has no equal. This interface that has placed us in tune with the autonomic nervous system of the patient and that allowed us to verify in the field the characteristics of neuromuscular manual therapy techniques adopted.

It obvious at this point to underline the importance of a potential therapeutic association between the classic rehabilitation methods used in the intensive care unit and neuromuscular approach of manual therapy. Anyway to confirm the positive effect of neuromuscular manual therapy on critical patients further studies are necessary in order to be able to consider this strategy like an additional treatment and / or alternative to traditional physiotherapy methods. It is interesting to highlight the results of another study [27] which have shown that a neuromuscular manual therapy, even carried out by members of the patient's family, previously trained, increased the patient's level of awareness of the same well as to provide an improvement of vital signs and the score GCS of these patients. There are few studies that show the importance of the participation of the family in providing care to patients admitted to intensive care.

The ICU is an unknown environment with so many unfamiliar subjects, and patients may seek a more family during hospitalization. The family members, in the context of their emotional support, are great motivators. In addition, their involvement should be recognized as an effective bridge between patients and medical staff.

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Corresponding Author:

Rosa Grazia Bellomo

Email: rbellomo@unich.it

Giovanni Barassi

Email: dottgiovannibarassi@gmail.com

Tullio Spina tullio.spina@ausl.pe.it

Matilde Del Duca

Email: matilde.delduca@yahoo.it

Piera Attilia Di Felice

Email: pieradf90@hotmail.it

Raoul Saggini

Email: saggini@unich.it

Email:

Conflict of interest:

The authors have declared no conflict of interest.